

LIVING THROUGH MENOPAUSE: RURAL TIBETAN WOMEN SPEAK

Rdo rje dpal 'byor རྗེ་དཔལ་འབྱོར། (Duoji huanjiao 多吉环角)

Rdo rje dpal 'byor རྗེ་དཔལ་འབྱོར། (Duoji huanjiao 多吉环角).
2024. Living Through Menopause: Rural Tibetan
Women Speak, *Asian Highland Perspectives* 1-13.
10.5281/zenodo.14286352

ABSTRACT

Despite the growing availability of medical care and health information in 2024, significant gaps in knowledge still need to be addressed about women's reproductive health in Tibetan rural communities. This study was undertaken in 2023, exploring the experiences, perceptions, and knowledge of menopause among six rural Tibetan women. Participants expressed general ignorance of menopause beyond it, typifying life in their forties and fifties. Neither the women nor their family members fully understood menopause symptoms and their potential mental and physical health impacts. Consequently, women often did not attribute discomfort to menopause. Some sought medical care when experiencing health issues, while others did so only when symptoms were severe. Cultural and religious practices were also relied upon to address symptoms. The six participants were born between 1945 and 1972 and were illiterate. Four had experienced menopause. Two were experiencing menopause. This study highlights the need for increased awareness and education on menopause in rural Tibetan communities.

KEYWORDS

Menopause, Tibetan women, discomfort from menopause, Tibetan menopause experience, Tibetan menopause perceptions

INTRODUCTION

This study explores the perceptions, practices, and experiences of menopause among Tibetan women in a rural agropastoral community. Lacking access to schools and formal education, nearly all locals born before 1990 were illiterate in this region. Women spent most of their lives raising children; herding sheep, goats, and cattle; and cultivating barley, wheat, and canola in isolation from the outside world with limited access to medical care and health information.

When faced with health challenges, these women typically visited the only Tibetan doctor in a neighboring village or traveled to the local township with limited medical resources. In addition to formal care, divination played an important role in their health practices. Locals often consulted *sngags pa* 'tantric practitioners', *bla ma*, or local *mo ba*¹ to determine what religious rituals to perform to address health issues.

With virtually no information about their reproductive health from a professional doctor, the women, busy with daily chores, commonly endured physical discomfort until their symptoms became severe. Some women neglected their health, unaware of the potential consequences. In 2024, while locals had greater access to medical care and women could receive hospital treatment more conveniently, there was not much information available to older women about menopause.

At the beginning of each interview of this study, women typically stated that there was nothing to say about menopause, displaying indifference and a lack of interest. When asked questions,² they responded that they had little to share, claiming they experienced little discomfort during menopause.

¹ A person who can predict the future or know the causes of an illness, often using prayer beads or a small box containing several tiny stones, and who offers religious solutions.

² See the Appendix for the questions that the women were asked in Tibetan.

My interest in this subject began when I read an article by Susan Dominus (2023), who told the story of a woman frustrated over the lack of effective treatment when she was experiencing traumatic and difficult menopausal symptoms. Although I was aware of menopause, this was the first time I understood how significantly it could impact a woman's health. This encounter motivated me to explore the menopausal experiences of local Tibetan women.

Traditional women's experiences of physical and reproductive health, particularly menopause, are often neglected or forgotten. Many people, including local women and men and healthcare workers, need to be made aware of how social and cultural contexts shape women's understanding and practices related to their health. There is a distinct local perspective and knowledge regarding healthcare in rural communities. Despite the global availability of advanced medical technologies and knowledge, many experience a significant gap between their understanding of menopause and their lived experience of its manifestations. This paper explores how local women perceive and experience menopause.

METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on the experiences and perceptions of *zla mtshan chad pa*³ 'cessation of menstruation'/'menopause' of six illiterate Tibetan women born between 1945 and 1972 from the rural areas of Bon skor (Wangshenke) Community, Bya mdo (Shagou) Township, Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. The study focused on women who had experienced menopause or were currently undergoing it, representing a range of menopausal experiences.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted using guiding questions between February 2023 and June 2024. Participants were free to express themselves openly. Interviewees were not obliged to respond to questions and could choose not to. Interviews were conducted respectfully and with cultural sensitivity in the A mdo Tibetan dialect. All participants provided informed consent to participate in the study. Before the interviews, each participant was asked for permission to share their experiences and to have their voices recorded via phone, to which all agreed. Participants' names were changed to protect their privacy, though the provided birth years are accurate.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Menopause is a natural biological process marking the end of a woman's reproductive years. It is marked by the cessation, slow or abrupt, of monthly menstruation because of the loss of ovarian follicular function (World Health Organization 2022).⁴ It typically occurs in a woman's forties and fifties, with the mean age of onset around fifty-one (Mayo Clinic 2021).⁵ Menopause typically lasts about seven years but might extend to fourteen years, depending on lifestyle choices and onset age (National Institute on Aging 2020).⁶ Symptoms range from physical to psychological manifestations. They might include hot flashes and night sweats, disturbed sleep, fatigue, depression, cognitive difficulties, heightened anxiety, joint pain, skin and eye dryness, and changes in skin and hair, impacting women's overall well-being (Talaulikar 2022).

The prevalence of menopausal symptoms and age of onset vary between geographical regions and are linked to overall health, employment status, socioeconomic background, past experiences (Palacios et al. 2010), race, and ethnicity (El Khoudary 2020).

³ This local term is used to describe menopause.

⁴ <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause>, accessed 18 April 2024.

⁵ Mayo Clinic. (2021). Menopause. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/menopause/symptoms-causes/syc-20353397>, accessed 18 April 2024.

⁶ <https://www.nia.nih.gov/health/menopause/what-menopause>, accessed 18 April 2024.

Tibetan Medicine provides insights into climacteric symptoms. While Tibetan medical terminology exists, there is a tendency to adopt biomedical terms for precision and convenience. Many contemporary Tibetan doctors understand *rlung tshabs* to be what biomedicine refers to as 'menopausal syndrome' (Tshe dbyang 2014). According to an early Tibetan physician (G.yu thog yon tan mgon po 2006 [1982]:375), menstruation is closely connected to *rlung tshabs* and exacerbated by such factors as psychological stress, childbirth, sexual activity, uterine bleeding, and malnutrition, resulting in joint pain, anxiety, dizziness, trembling flesh, numbness, and irregular menstruation.

Treatment options for menopausal symptoms vary across cultures and medical knowledge. Overall, the literature on menopause in Tibetan, Chinese, and English includes five main areas. The first area explores menopausal treatments, including Western Medicine, Chinese Traditional Medicine, Tibetan Medicine, and physical activities such as yoga. The second area scrutinizes these medical interventions' effectiveness. The third area focuses on factors such as geographical location, lifestyle, and altitude that impact women's menopausal symptoms. The fourth and fifth areas analyze the onset age of menopause across diverse regions and the menopausal experiences of women from various ethnic backgrounds.

Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of hormone therapy (HT) in alleviating menopausal symptoms such as hot flashes and night sweats (Flores, Pal, and Manson 2021), which has significantly reduced the frequency and severity of these symptoms (Mayo Clinic 2021).⁷ However, this option is rarely available to Tibetan women.

Despite its efficacy, HT has potential risks and side effects that have been extensively researched. A major concern is the increased risk of cardiovascular events, including stroke and blood clots (National Institute on Aging 2021),⁸ and an increased risk of breast cancer (Beral et al. 2003). Studies have shown that the risks outweigh the benefits of using HT, highlighting the importance of careful consideration and individualized decision-making (Writing Group for the Women's Health Initiative Investigators 2002). Exploring alternative therapies with fewer side effects, such as Tibetan Medicine, is an ideal option, given the adverse reactions of HT (Cai 2011).

Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of Tibetan Medicine in reducing symptoms when administered to patients over time (Wanma ji and Jimao jia 2018, Cai Zang Ji and Duo jie Cairang 2023).

A primary approach to addressing menopausal symptoms in Tibetan Medicine involves addressing irregular menstrual cycle and administering supplementary treatment of *rlung* 'wind', *mkhris ba* 'bile', and *bad kan* 'phlegm' based on specific menopausal symptoms (Cuoji 2013, Hu 2017). Additionally, *me btsa* 'Tibetan moxibustion'⁹ is promoted along with Tibetan herbal medicines such as '*ol se nyer lnga*', '*sems bde*', and '*a gar so lnga*' with dietary restrictions on spicy, sour, oily, raw, and cold foods, and encouraging physical exercises to promote blood circulation, alleviating symptoms (Qi 2022).

According to one experiment, Tibetan herbal Medicine *se 'bru* 'pomegranate' can reduce menopausal symptoms without side effects (Tong 2008).

Traditional Chinese Medicine concludes that menopause is associated with a decline in kidney function and an imbalance between Yin and Yang, so treatment focuses on nourishing kidney function and rebalancing Yin and Yang (Wang and Yu 2021, Yu 2018).

Yoga practice has been found to alleviate insomnia and climacteric symptoms (Afonso et al. 2012, Khalsa 2004) engendered by the menopause cycle, such as psychological, vasomotor,

⁷ <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/menopause/in-depth/hormone-therapy/art-20046372>, accessed 18 April 2024.

⁸ <https://www.nia.nih.gov/health/menopause/hot-flashes-what-can-i-do>, accessed 19 April 2024.

⁹ A fire healing therapy involving burning moxa (dried mugwort) on particular points of the body to help positive energy circulation <https://newyuthok.it/en/tibetan-moxibustion-seminar/>, accessed 18 April 2024.

and somatic symptoms (Permatasari 2018). Yoga practice may promote estrogen hormone and endocrine systems in menopausal women, which may lead to lessening menopausal symptoms such as hot flashes, night sweats, anxiety, and sleep difficulties (Archong and Plianbangchang 2021, Chattha et al. 2008, Afonso et al. 2016:11). However, more research is needed to determine if yoga effectively treats menopausal symptoms (Lee et al. 2009).

In Tibetan areas of China, altitude has been identified as a protective factor against osteopenia and osteoporosis in postmenopausal women, with high altitude associated with elevated bone mass irregularities and a lower incidence of osteoporosis (Zhong et al., 2023). Reduced pulse oxygen saturation in post-menopausal women at high altitudes is attributed to ovarian function cessation rather than chronological age (Gonzales and Villena 2000). Another study observed that women in high-altitude Himalayan regions experience menopause at 46.8 years and menarche at 16.2 years, indicating a consistent trend of early menopause and delayed menarche among this population (Beall 1981).

Wang et al. (2022) investigated menopausal women from various ethnic groups in China and suggested that menopause-related symptoms vary among ethnic groups. A higher level of female status in the family and family support may reduce menopause-related symptoms in middle-aged women.

Qiong et al. (2023) explored the stigmatization experiences of Chinese women experiencing menopause and suggested they suffer physically and mentally within their families. For instance, one participant mentioned that her husband accused her of mental illness when she expressed cervical spine discomfort. Another participant shared how her husband forbade her from seeking medical care when she had joint pain.

Enhancing healthcare professionals' understanding of menopausal hormone therapy is essential to addressing the needs of the growing menopausal population in China (Lin, Feng, and Yu 2020). More research is needed to explore the intersection of menopause, work, and health within organizational contexts, as menopause remains unaddressed due to societal barriers (fear of ridicule, stigmatization, and stereotypes) and lack of recognition (Verdonk, Bendien, and Appelman 2022).

Despite extensive research on menopause, few studies examine Tibetan women's experiences, knowledge, and perspectives of this life stage. More research is needed on how Tibetan women perceive menopause and how cultural beliefs and limited access to resources and professional medical care shape how they understand it. This paper explores the experiences of Tibetan women experiencing menopause, the range of symptoms experienced, their awareness of the process itself, and their knowledge about strategies for effective management of the symptoms.

INTERVIEWS

Lha mo rgya (b. 1972, age 52)

I am fifty-two years old and haven't yet undergone menopause. I think this is good. Local women think it is a disadvantage if a woman has her menopause at an early age, like in one's forties, believing it results in physical issues later. For example, my mother-in-law (who has passed away) couldn't see well after her menopause at forty-five.

I think I will have my menopause in the next few years. I don't have many premenopausal symptoms, but an obvious change was my menstrual cycle becoming irregular when I turned forty-six. Sometimes, menstruation comes earlier, and sometimes it is delayed. I thought something was wrong and consulted a Tibetan doctor who took my pulse and prescribed Tibetan herbal medicine. My period became regular for some time. However, later, I didn't menstruate for two months. Although I was concerned that I might have menopause at an early age, I didn't go to the hospital. Finally, my periods resumed. Women around me all hope they will have their menopause in their fifties.

I have never received care, financial, or emotional support from my husband, who spends his time roaming around and drinking alcohol. I no longer expect him to care about me. However, my

children care about my health, though I often avoid burdening them with unnecessary concerns. In addition, our community has never organized events to provide healthcare information about menopause or other topics, but they once offered free physical check-ups.

When I was around forty-three, I couldn't see clearly, felt dizzy, and often had headaches. I then went to the local county town with my daughter-in-law, who could speak Chinese, and we consulted a Chinese doctor who checked my blood pressure and tested my blood. I was diagnosed with hypertension. The doctor prescribed biomedicine to lower my blood pressure. It alleviated my symptoms. Later, some people around me said taking biomedicine for the long term is not good, so I replaced it with Tibetan medicine. I also tried to be cautious with my diet, reducing my consumption of meat, milk, and butter. Now, I am nearly recovered from high blood pressure. I think these symptoms might be related to my experience of menopause at an early age.

I occasionally feel stressed and distressed and become absent-minded. I don't have hot flashes, but it they are common for some women I know. For example, my sister-in-law, who is in her forties, was alone one night and came to stay at my home. She told me she had a tough time with sudden heat in her body, especially her palms and soles, and was damp from sweat. At the time, we didn't know these were premenopausal symptoms.

I rarely hear women around me discuss or attach much importance to menopause. We don't know much about it. No medical workers told me about menopause symptoms. However, local women do often say that it's not good to have menopause early because it leads to health issues or diseases. Instead, it's good to have it later in their fifties.

Today, women don't often visit each other's homes for intimate talks like they used to because we have smartphones through which we see the world.

I am not worried about menopause and hope I won't experience menopause until I'm in my late fifties.

Klu mo (b. 1960, age 64)

I have nothing to say about menopause. I had my menopause at forty-four. I thought I was pregnant at first and went to see a doctor who said I was experiencing menopause.

I didn't know menopause indicators, and I didn't have any of the symptoms you just mentioned. I never worried about menopause and did not consider it a significant transition. The only thing I heard from local women was it was not good to have it early because that caused eye issues and affected the heart.

I had no negative health conditions after menopause.

Bsod b+he (b. 1963, age 61)

I went through menopause at the age of forty-six and felt liberated from the abdominal pain, exhaustion, and discomfort I experienced during menstruation.

I experienced hot flashes, anxiety, exhaustion, and irregular menstrual cycles, but I didn't realize they were related to menopause at the time. I mostly brushed them off, and when they became severe, I visited a doctor who prescribed Tibetan medicine after taking my pulse. My husband and children care about my health, but I usually don't share much with them. They are all busy with their responsibilities and making a living.

Years after menopause, I had joint pain and was diagnosed with hyperostosis. For this, I tried Tibetan therapies like acupuncture and moxibustion, which somewhat helped alleviate my backache and joint pain for a short time. My doctor also recommended that I sleep on a hard rather than a soft mattress.

When I experience heart issues, I often find solace in prostrating and circumambulating at religious sites, which calms my mind. I've heard from older women that early menopause can lead to health issues like eye problems and joint pain, but they rarely mention other symptoms associated with menopause.

Sgron mtsho (b.1945, age 79)

I don't remember much about my menopause. I ignored it because my daily life was full of house chores, herding, and farming. I had no time to care about it.

I didn't have any issues before and after menopause. Menopause can bring comfort and freedom to women. We no longer need to care and worry about how to deal with menstruation every month.

I once consulted a Tibetan doctor in another community for Tibetan cough medicine. When he asked me about my menopause, I was ashamed to talk about it. He advised me not to take many contraceptive drugs, which would cause gynecological issues. He said many women came to him for medicine because of heavy menstruation.

I don't recall discussing menopause with local women. We didn't regard it as important.

Mkhar mo (b. 1970, age 54)

I witnessed several cases of women in their forties whose menstruation stopped for one to two years and then returned, which finally led to their deaths from excessive bleeding. This used to happen among local women who generally say that early menopause is not good and that it's important to have a physical examination after menopause begins.

I am fifty-five now. Most women my age have already experienced menopause. I believe my menopause will happen soon as my cycles have become irregular, which my doctor says is a sign of impending menopause. I've been dealing with various physical symptoms, including occasional hot flashes when I feel a sudden wave of heat and begin to sweat, especially my palms and soles. These episodes usually subside after a few minutes. It's been almost four years since my hot flashes began. They continue to this day, which has affected my mental well-being.

Over the past few years, I've become forgetful. I often find myself standing somewhere, not knowing what I'm doing. In addition, I've become emotional and emotionally vulnerable.

When I visited doctors in the local county town, they didn't attribute these issues to perimenopause. Instead, they prescribed medication based on the symptoms.

I also experience chest tightness and shortness of breath. My voice trembles when I talk to people, and I suspect it's due to a heart issue. However, when I went to the provincial hospital and had an electrocardiogram, no heart problems were diagnosed. The doctor suggested my symptoms were partly due to menopause, and I was prescribed a month's worth of biomedicine, which didn't relieve my symptoms, so I stopped taking it.

In addition, I regularly have pain in my back, knees, and pelvis. After having an X-ray, I was diagnosed with abnormal bone growth. Afterward, I've used ointments and medicinal patches, which provide temporary pain relief. I've also undergone Tibetan medical therapies like *skam khab* 'acupuncture' and *me btsa'* 'moxibustion'. I took biomedicine, which can alleviate my joint pain when it becomes severe.

To cure the pain, my husband asked a *bla ma* for advice and had my family perform religious rituals and chanting. We invited monks to our house and completed all the rituals. I also took Tibetan medicines, which provided some relief, though the symptoms reoccur. It's hard to endure these frequent physical discomforts. No medicine offers lasting relief.

My family members care about my health and often take me to see doctors when I am ill, but I haven't received any particularly effective treatments. Neither the local community nor the government has organized events to provide information about menopause and other aspects of women's health.

Recently, I have been experiencing irregular menstrual bleeding, which is concerning. I'm particularly afraid of having heavy bleeding during menopause.

Some time ago, I experienced irregular bleeding that lasted for nearly fifteen days. I underwent a hysteroscopy after consulting a doctor, and an endometrial polyp was removed through dilation and

curettage. Initially, I was hesitant to undergo the procedure and tried using Chinese herbal medicine to stop the bleeding, but it was ineffective. Eventually, I decided to proceed with the surgery.

Following the procedure, Dydrogesterone tablets were prescribed to be taken for fourteen days each month starting from the first day of my period for six months. I was also asked to take calcium daily. I hope to navigate menopause without too much difficulty.

I've seen many doctors but haven't found any truly effective medicine. Some medications alleviate my symptoms temporarily, but the symptoms eventually return.

Rta mgrin (b. 1970, age 54)

I learned from local women that menopause typically occurs in our forties or fifties. Furthermore, they advised that if menstruation stops in one's forties, a visit to the hospital is recommended to ascertain whether it's due to menopause or other factors. However, if menstruation stops in one's fifties, it's generally considered normal. Unlike menarche, the onset of menopause is a topic openly discussed among local middle-aged women. But we don't regard it as an important issue causing severe problems.

I experienced menopause at forty-four, which raised concerns about early onset. Fortunately, I encountered no significant issues before or after the transition. For me, the process was gradual. Initially, my menstrual cycles stopped for three months, then resumed for five months before ceasing completely.

I went to see a doctor when my menstruation paused for three months. They recommended an ultrasound B test, though I didn't fully understand what they were checking. Later, the doctor assured me everything was fine and there was no need to worry. Many of us, local illiterate women, often don't know what medical reports mean and rely on what the doctor tells us.

During menopause, my whole body, especially my palms and soles, were abruptly hot, and I sweated occasionally for some minutes at a time. These symptoms lasted seven to eight years. Sometimes, I experienced hot flashes three or four times a day, but sometimes, they disappeared for a month or so, only to reoccur. I first thought I had a fever and was infected with tuberculosis, but this was not confirmed when I had a physical test. I didn't specifically consult a doctor for my hot flashes.

I also experienced heightened anxiety and irritability in response to loud noises, was persistently in a low mood, wanted to avoid social interactions, and felt overwhelmingly exhausted. It was a challenging period, made more difficult by no one understanding my condition. I was unaware that these symptoms were related to menopause. No local women or doctors had ever mentioned this association.

My family members genuinely care about my health, but I find it difficult to constantly share my usually mild symptoms with them unless they become severe. Additionally, there haven't been any instances where the local community has organized events to provide information about women's health.

At forty-six, I began experiencing joint pain, but I didn't pay much attention to it. Five years after menopause, I was diagnosed with abnormal fat levels in my blood, although I'm unsure if it was related to menopause. Additionally, I found it much easier to gain weight after menopause.

I consider it beneficial that I underwent menopause at an early age since I no longer had to deal with menstruation and reproduction. In this sense, I feel liberated and more like a man regarding bodily experiences.

A notable change after menopause was a shift in my feelings toward my husband. I found that I no longer experienced sexual desire for him. I often felt tired of his presence and experienced vaginal dryness.

Based on my observations, women around me seemed to have little awareness or concern about menopause and associated conditions. Also, I didn't meet medical professionals who discussed specific health issues related to menopause.

DISCUSSION

We gain insight into the attitudes and understandings of menopause among local women in rural Tibetan areas of China through the voices of the six women interviewed. Their experiences offer a glimpse into their generation's shared knowledge and beliefs, shaped by long-term interactions with one another in daily life.

All participants understood that menopause signified the end of their menstrual cycle, marking the cessation of fertility, typically occurring in their forties or fifties. However, they were unaware menopause could lead to certain physical discomforts or symptoms. At the beginning of the interviews, all the women claimed they had not experienced any physical or emotional discomfort during menopause. However, when presented with a description of recognized conditions such as anxiety, hot flashes, joint pain, and irregular periods, they realized they had indeed experienced some of these discomforts but had not linked them to menopause.

While local women do discuss menopause, it wasn't a topic frequently brought up in conversation, possibly because it was seen as unimportant. One participant mentioned feeling embarrassed discussing her symptoms with a doctor. There was also a shared belief among the women that the early onset of menopause might lead to health problems such as eye issues and joint pain. Consequently, they regarded late menopause as preferable, although some felt that early onset was liberating.

Healthcare professionals had not informed any of the women that certain symptoms were linked to menopause. When they visited doctors, they were not told that what they reported was related to menopause. Instead, treatments were based on their specific complaints, and diagnosis was often made by taking their pulse. Some women sought medical help when they experienced irregular periods or after their menstruation stopped, while others had no physical examinations. Some only sought medical help when their symptoms became severe.

One participant, who had been experiencing significant physical and emotional challenges, sought medical help from various doctors. A doctor at a provincial hospital prescribed biomedicine for menopause, but it had little effect. Despite trying multiple medications, she found little relief. Her family regularly performed religious rituals and chanting to help alleviate her condition, which provided some emotional comfort and a sense of healing.

In terms of treatment, in addition to biomedical interventions and Tibetan medical therapies such as acupuncture and moxibustion, religious practices played a crucial role in managing physical and emotional discomfort. Local women commonly performed prostrations and circumambulation as remedies that could alleviate their anxiety and provide emotional solace.

For some women, the end of menopause symbolized liberation from physical discomforts such as abdominal pain associated with menstruation. However, one participant expressed concern about the potential dangers of menopause, stressing that women should take it seriously, as it could lead to severe complications like excessive bleeding, which she believed had caused the deaths of local women due to a lack of awareness.

One participant mentioned experiencing symptoms of vaginal dryness and a significant reduction in sexual desire, which had affected her relationship with her husband.

This study discovers a disturbing lack of information and awareness among participants. Almost none of the women interviewed received information about menopause from local healthcare workers or other sources, nor had they attended any meetings focused on women's health. Furthermore, the women lacked comprehensive knowledge of menopause and its potential discomforts beyond the cessation of menstruation in their fifties, underscoring an urgent need for improved education initiatives in this area.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights local women's need to correctly understand menopause, its indicators, and effective coping methods. Without proper knowledge, women who experience significant physical and emotional challenges may not attribute these issues to menopause and might take unnecessary medications.

Many women lack awareness of how to manage menopausal challenges effectively, often internalizing their struggles and enduring avoidable suffering due to misconceptions. Without a contemporary, informed perspective, these challenges can adversely affect their personal well-being and family relationships. This study underscores the need to improve women's health education, particularly concerning menopause treatments, to enhance their overall health and quality of life.

To achieve this, governments might organize programs and disseminate accurate healthcare knowledge in a culturally respectful manner. Furthermore, educating students in schools would encourage empathy and understanding toward mothers and other women, encouraging greater support during this vulnerable life stage.

This study's limitations include focusing exclusively on the experiences of six local women. To develop a more comprehensive understanding of menopausal experiences, future research should include a larger and more diverse group of participants. Additionally, examining men's understanding and attitudes toward menopausal women, as well as identifying cultural barriers, would provide valuable insights into the social environment women navigate and the support they receive during menopause.

Further areas of exploration might include the use of Tibetan medicine or other traditional remedies for managing menopausal symptoms, as well as the role of religion and spirituality in helping women cope with the emotional and physical changes of menopause. Such investigations could offer deeper and more valuable insights into how cultural, traditional, and spiritual factors influence women's experiences and well-being during this significant life transition.

REFERENCES

- Afonso, Rui Ferreira, Helena Hachul, Elisa Harumi Kozasa, Denise de Souza Oliveira, Viviane Goto, Dinah Rodrigues, Sérgio Tufik, and José Roberto Leite. 2012. Yoga Decreases Insomnia in Postmenopausal Women: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Menopause* 19(2):186-193.
https://journals.lww.com/menopausejournal/abstract/2012/02000/yoga_decreases_in_somnia_in_postmenopausal_women_a.13.aspx, accessed 5 May 2024
- Afonso, Rui Ferreira, Elisa Harumi Kozasa, Dinah Rodrigues, José Roberto Leite, Sérgio Tufik, and Helena Hachul. 2016. Yoga Increased Serum Estrogen Levels in Postmenopausal Women—A Case Report. *Menopause* 23(5):584-586.
https://journals.lww.com/menopausejournal/abstract/2016/05000/yoga_increased_serum_estrogen_levels_in.18.aspx, accessed 5 May 2024
- Archong, Natsupa and Samlee Plianbangchang. 2021. The Effectiveness of Tibetan Yoga Toward Estrogen Hormone Levels: A Community-based Randomized Controlled Trial. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications* 3(11): 16-23.
<http://ijmr.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/IJMRAP-V3N10P117Y21.pdf>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Beall, Cynthia M. 1981. Growth in a Population of Tibetan Origin at High Altitude. *Annals of Human Biology* 8(1):31-38.

- <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03014468100004761>, accessed, 5 May 2024
- Beral, Valerie, Emily Banks, Gillian Reeves, and Diana Bull. 2003. Breast Cancer and Hormone-Replacement Therapy: The Million Women Study. *The Lancet* 362(9392), 1330-1331. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(03\)14596-5/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(03)14596-5/fulltext), accessed 5 May 2024
- Cai Xiuqin 蔡秀清. 2011. Zanyao zhiliao wei juejingqi zonghezheng 60 li linchuang guan cha 藏药治围绝经期综合征 60 例临床观察[J] [Clinical Observation of 60 Cases of Treating Perimenopausal Syndrome with Tibetan Medicine]. *Zhongguo minzu yiyao zazhi 中国民族医药杂志 [Journal of Medicine & Pharmacy of Chinese Minorities]* 12:18-19. https://www.zhangqiaokeyan.com/academic-journal-cn_journal-medicine-pharmacy-chinese-minorities_thesis/0201219626652.html, accessed 5 May 2024
- Cai zang ji 才藏吉, Duo jie Cairang 多杰才让. 2023. Gengnianqi zonghezheng caiyong zangyi zhiliao de liaoxiao yanxi 更年期综合征采用藏医治疗的疗效研析[J] [Analysis on the Efficacy of Tibetan Medicine Treatment for Menopausal Syndrome]. *Zhongguo keji qikan shujuku yiyao 中国科技期刊数据库医药 [China Science and Technology Journal Database, Medicine]*. https://www.nstl.gov.cn/paper_detail.html?id=58163ccb38b34df14f6663b16aa82b2a, accessed 20 November 2024
- Chattha, Ritu, Nagarathna Raghuram, Padmalatha Venkatram, and Nagendra R. Hongasandra. 2008. Treating the Climacteric Symptoms in Indian Women with an Integrated Approach to Yoga Therapy: A Randomized Control Study. *Menopause* 15(5):862-870. https://journals.lww.com/menopausejournal/abstract/2008/15050/treating_the_climacteric_symptoms_in_indian_women.11.aspx, accessed 5 May 2024
- Cuo Ji 措吉. 2013. Zangyi zhiliao gengnianqi zonghezheng liaoxiao guan cha 藏医治疗更年期综合征疗效观察[J] [Observation on the Efficacy of Tibetan Medicine in Treating Menopausal Syndrome]. *Zhongguo minzu yiyao zazhi 中国民族医药杂志 [Journal of Medicine & Pharmacy of Chinese Minorities]* 19(7):5-6. DOI:10.3969/j.issn.1006-6810.2013.07.004. https://www.nstl.gov.cn/paper_detail.html?id=5f2766aob5728af6e86e7e5dc022b1d2, accessed 5 May 2024
- Dominus, Susan. 2023. Women Have Been Misled About Menopause. *New York Times*, 15 June 2023. <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/02/01/magazine/menopause-hot-flashes-hormone-therapy.html>, accessed 22 October 2024
- El Khoudary, Samar R. 2020. Age At Menopause Onset and Risk of Cardiovascular Disease Around the World. *Maturitas* 141:33-38. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0378512220302966>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Flores, Valerie A., Lubna Pal, and JoAnn E. Manson. 2021. Hormone Therapy in Menopause: Concepts, Controversies, and Approach to Treatment. *Endocrine Reviews* 42(6):720-752. <https://doi.org/10.1210/edrev/bnab011> accessed 20 April 2024
- G.yu thog yon tan mgon po གཡུ་ཐོག་ཡོན་ཏན་མགོན་པོ། 2006 [1982]. *Bdud rtsi snying po yan lag brgyad pa gsang ba man ngag gi rgyud ces bya ba bzhugs so* བདུད་རྩི་སྤྱིང་བོ་ཡན་ལག་བརྒྱུད་པ་གསང་བ་མན་ངག་གྱི་རྒྱུད་ཅེས་བྲུ་བ་བྲལ་གསལ་སྟོ། [The Tantra Lineage, the Eighth Section of Medical Compound Potency Compendium]. Lha sa ལྷ་ས་: Bod ljong mi dmangs dpe skrun khang བོད་རྫོང་ས་མི་དམངས་དབུས་སྐྱོན་ཁང་། [Tibet People's Press].
- Gonzales, G F and A Villena. 2000. Low Pulse Oxygen Saturation In Post-menopausal Women at High Altitude is Related to a High Serum Testosterone/estradiol Ratio. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 71(2):147-154.

- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0020729200002708>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Hu, Xianjin, Xin Zhang, Zhipeng Zhang, Xinran Li, Qiling Gou, Runyu Ye, and Xiaoping Chen. 2022. Relationship Between Lipid Parameters and Vascular Mechanical Characteristics Among a Normotensive Population Without Diabetes Mellitus Residing at the Qinghai–Tibet Plateau: A Cross-sectional Study. *BMC Cardiovascular Disorders* 22:357. *BMC Cardiovasc Discord* 22, 357 (2022). <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12872-022-02801-8>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Hu Yanqin 胡燕芹. 2017. Zangyao zhiliao longxing funv gengnianqi zonghezheng de liaoxiao guan cha 藏药治疗隆型妇女更年期综合征的疗效观察[J] [Clinical Observation on the Efficacy of Tibetan Medicine in Treating Long-Type Menopausal Syndrome in Women]. *Zhongwai nuxing jiankang yanjiu 中外女性健康研究 [Women's Health Research]* 7:97-98. https://xueshu.baidu.com/usercenter/paper/show?paperid=867c7da0dd019d5dbb4fa7bc94eaa0a2&site=xueshu_se&hitarticle=1, accessed 5 May 2024
- Khalsa, Sat Bir S. 2004. Treatment of Chronic Insomnia with Yoga: A Preliminary Study With Sleep–wake Diaries. *Applied Psychophysiology and Biofeedback* 29:269-278. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10484-004-0387-0>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Lee, Myeong Soo, Jong-In Kim, Jeong Yong Ha, Kate Boddy, and Edzard Ernst. 2009. Yoga for Menopausal Symptoms: A Systematic Review. *Menopause* 16(3):602-608. https://journals.lww.com/menopausejournal/abstract/2009/16030/yoga_for_menopausal_symptoms_a_systematic_review.31.aspx, accessed 5 May 2024
- Lin, L., P Feng, and Q Yu. 2020. Attitude and Knowledge for Menopause Management Among Health Professionals in Mainland China. *Climacteric* 23(6):614-621. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13697137.2020.1775809?scroll=top&needAccess=true>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Mayo Clinic. 2021. Hormone Therapy for Women's Health: Is It Right for You? <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/menopause/in-depth/hormone-therapy/art-20046372>, accessed 22 April 2024
- Palacios, S, VW Henderson, N Siseles, D Tan, and P Villaseca. 2010. Age of Menopause and Impact of Climacteric Symptoms by Geographical Region. *Climacteric*, 13(5):419-428. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.3109/13697137.2010.507886>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Permatasari, Denise. 2018. Yoga for Menopausal Symptoms: A Review in *3rd ASEAN Conference on Psychology, Counselling, and Humanities (ACPOCH 2017)*, 251-255. Atlantis Press. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/acpoch-17/25890710>, accessed, 5 May 2024
- Qi Guoxiu 祁国秀. 2020. Gengnianqi zonghezheng huanzhe de zangyi huli 更年期综合症患者的藏医护理[J] [Tibetan Medical Care for Patients with Menopausal Syndrome]. *Zhongxiyi jiehe xinxueguan bing dianzi zazhi 中西医结合心血管病电子杂志 [Cardiovascular Disease Electronic Journal of Integrated Traditional Chinese and Western Medicine]* 8(14):125,153. <https://xueshu.baidu.com/usercenter/paper/show?paperid=15130te06n460je09h6500qoqt456644>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Qiong Li, Jintu Gu, Jianyuan Huang, Pei Zhao, and Chenliang Luo 2023. They See Me As Mentally Ill: The Stigmatization Experiences of Chinese Menopausal Women in the Family. *BMC Women's Health* 23(1):185. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12905-023-02350-y>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Talaulikar, Vikram. 2022. Menopause Transition: Physiology and Symptoms. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology* 81:3-7.

- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1521693422000426>, accessed 5 May 2024
- Tong yan 童妍, Wang Zhihao 王志豪, and Wu Xiaqing 吴晓青. 2008. Zangyao sezhu zhiliao gengnianqi zonghezheng de shiyan yanjiu 藏药色珠治疗更年期综合征的实验研究[J]. [Experimental Study on the Treatment of Menopausal Syndrome with Tibetan Medicine Sezhu] *Zhongguo yaoye 中国药业 [China Pharmaceuticals]* 1(2) DOI:CNKI:SUN:YGGZ.O.2008-01-002. <https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/periodical/zgmzyyzz201307004>, accessed 6 May 2024
- Tshe dbyangs ཚེ་དབྱངས། 2014. *Bod lugs gso ba rig p'i mo bad rlung tshabs dang phyi lugs gso rig gi bud med rgan dus phyogs bsdus bad gzhi'i dbar gyi 'brel ba dpyad pa བོད་ལྷགས་གསོ་བ་རིག་པའི་ཚོན་དང་རྒྱ་ཆབས་དང་ཕྱི་ལྷགས་གསོ་བ་རིག་གི་བྱུང་མཛད་ཀྱི་རྒྱན་དུས་ཚྱུགས་བསྐྱེས་ནད་གཞིའི་དབར་ཕྱི་འབྲེལ་བ་དབྱུང་པ། [Research on the Relationship Between Rlungtsab of Tibetan Medicine and Menopausal Syndrome of Western Medicine] Doctoral dissertation. 北京中医药大学 [Beijing University of Chinese Medicine].*
- Verdonk, Petra, Elena Bendien, and Yolande Appelman. 2022. Menopause and Work: A Narrative Literature Review About Menopause, Work and Health. *Work* 72(2):483-496. <https://content.iospress.com/articles/work/wor205214>, accessed 6 May 2024
- Wang, Jinyi, Yezhe Lin, Limin Gao, Xingjun Li, Chunhua He, Maosheng Ran, and Xudong Zhao. 2022. Menopause-related Symptoms and Influencing Factors in Mosuo, Yi, and Han Middle-aged Women in China. *Frontiers in Psychology* 13:763596. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.763596/full>, accessed 6 May 2024
- Wang, YP and Q Yu. 2021. The Treatment of Menopausal Symptoms by Traditional Chinese Medicine in Asian Countries. *Climacteric* 24(1):64-67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13697137.2020.1832461>, accessed 19 April 2024
- Wanma ji 完么吉, Jimao jia 吉毛加. 2018. Zangyi zhiliao gengnianqi zonghezheng liaoxiao guan cha 藏医治疗更年期综合征疗效观察[J] [Efficacy Observation of Tibetan Medicine in Treating Menopausal Syndrome]. *Yangsheng baojian zhinan 养生保健指南 [Health Guide]* 29:268. DOI:10.3969/j.issn.1006-6845.2018.29.261. https://xueshu.baidu.com/usercenter/paper/show?paperid=1w440mworg0304m05m5j0a60s8395082&site=xueshu_se, accessed 6 May 2024
- Writing Group for the Women's Health Initiative Investigators. 2002. Risks and Benefits of Estrogen Plus Progestin in Healthy Postmenopausal Women: Principal Results from the Women's Health Initiative Randomized Controlled Trial. *Jama* 288(3):321-333. <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/195120>, accessed 22 April 2024
- Yu, Qi. 2018. Traditional Chinese Medicine: Perspectives on and Treatment of Menopausal Symptoms. *Climacteric* 21(2):93-95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13697137.2018.1434983>, accessed 20 April 2024
- Zhong, Huaichang, Yaxi Zhou, Peng Wang, Qundi Jia, Yang Wan, and Hai Xiong. 2023. Influencing Factors of Bone Mass Abnormalities Among Postmenopausal Women in Tibet, China. *BMC Public Health* 23(1):2100. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12889-023-17015-6>, accessed 6 May 2024

TIBETAN TERMS

'ol se nyer lnga འོ་སེ་ཉེར་ལྷན།
a gar so lnga ཨ་གར་སོ་ལྷན།
bad kan བད་ཀན།
bla ma ལྷ་མ།
bsod b+he བསོད་བློ།
bya mdo བྱ་མདོ།
g.yu thog yon tan mgon po གཡུ་ཐོག་ཡོན་ཏན་མགོན་པོ།
klu mo ལྷ་མོ།
lha mo rgyal ལྷ་མོ་རྒྱལ།
mang ra མང་ར།
me btsa' མེ་བཙའ།
mkhar mo མཁར་མོ།
mkhris ba མཁྲིས་པ།
mo ba མོ་བ།
mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།
rlung ལྷུང།
rlung tshabs ལྷུང་ཚབས།
rta mgrin ཏྲ་མགོན།
se 'bru སེ་འབྲུ།
sems bde སེམས་བདེ།
sgron mtsho སྐྱོན་མཚོ།
skam khab སྐམ་ཁབ།
sngags pa སྔགས་པ།
zla mtshan chad pa ལྷ་མཚན་ཚད་པ།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南
Hainan 海南
Qinghai 青海
Shagou 沙沟
yang 阳
yin 阴

APPENDIX: QUESTIONS THAT THE WOMEN WERE ASKED IN TIBETAN

1. How is menopause understood or discussed in your community?
2. Did you talk to other women who had experienced menopause? Did their experiences influence your understanding or approach?
3. Was it easy to access medical care for menopause-related concerns?
4. What symptoms did you experience during or before menopause? Did you seek medical advice? If so, how did doctors deal with it?
5. Did you experience symptoms like hot flashes, sleeplessness, depression, anxiety, memory issues, and mood swings?
6. Did you share your experiences or symptoms with anyone during menopause?
7. How long did your symptoms last?
8. Did menopausal symptoms or discomfort affect your daily life? If so, how?
9. At what age did you experience menopause?
10. Do women in your community consider menopause an important issue?
11. Was menopause a challenging experience for you?
12. Did you feel worried or anxious about the onset of menopause?
13. Did your family, friends, or community support you during menopause?
14. Are there traditional methods or remedies used locally to manage menopausal symptoms?